

Photoelectrochemical generation of H₂O₂ using hematite (α-Fe₂O₃) and gas diffusion electrode (GDE)

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ABSTRACT

In contrast to the industrial-scale production of H₂O₂, electrochemical or photoelectrochemical synthesis is an environmentally friendly alternative. In this study, the photoelectrochemical generation of H₂O₂ was investigated using a hematite (α-Fe₂O₃/FTO/glass) photoanode in combination with a gas diffusion electrode (GDE) modified by the incorporation of tin(II) phthalocyanine (SnPc) in its hydrophilic layer. The experiments were conducted in a photoelectrochemical cell with two compartments separated by a proton exchange membrane, under an applied bias and AM1.5 irradiation (100 mW/cm²). The amount of H₂O₂ generated was quantified through chemical analysis using visible light spectrophotometry of the electrolyte. To assess the process efficiency, the Faradaic efficiency (FE) was calculated. The optimal configuration employed air as the inlet gas for the GDE and phosphate buffer (pH 6.4) as the electrolyte in the cathodic compartment. The combination of the hematite photoanode and the GDE modified with SnPc was the most effective for H₂O₂ photoelectrochemical generation. The highest FE values achieved were 52.4 % for the GDE (O₂ reduction to H₂O₂) and 0.4 % for the hematite photoanode (H₂O oxidation to H₂O₂).

1. Introduction

Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) has extensive applications across various industrial sectors, playing a significant role in both the chemical industry and environmental protection initiatives. Its use results in water as a byproduct, making it a key contributor to eco-friendly practices in the chemical industry. The industrial-scale production of hydrogen peroxide predominantly relies on the anthraquinone oxidation (AO) process, which is catalyzed by the rare metal palladium (Pd).

However, due to its inherent drawbacks, the AO process cannot be considered environmentally friendly. This method involves a series of steps, including the hydrogenation and oxidation of an alkylanthraquinone precursor dissolved in a mixture of harmful organic solvents. Subsequently, liquid-liquid extraction is used to recover hydrogen peroxide. These factors negatively affect both its sustainability and production costs. Additionally, the transportation, storage, and handling of bulk quantities of hydrogen peroxide pose safety risks and lead to escalating expenses [1]. As a result, researchers are actively exploring innovative and more environmentally friendly methods for producing hydrogen peroxide. One promising alternative to the AO process is the photoelectrochemical (PEC) production of hydrogen peroxide, which

can be achieved through two processes: the oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) and the water oxidation reaction (WOR).

While numerous studies have focused on the generation of H₂O₂ through the ORR (Eq. (1)) [2–5], comparatively less emphasis has been placed on the WOR for H₂O₂ production (Eq. (2)), such as on TiO₂ [6], BiVO₄ [6], or WO₃ [7]. As the reverse process of the ORR, the WOR also involves a multielectron mechanism. In photoelectrochemical water oxidation reactions, the evolution of H₂O₂ (Eq. (2)) is thermodynamically less favorable compared to O₂ evolution (Eq. (3)), with the potential difference between E(H₂O₂/H₂O) and E(O₂/H₂O) being 0.547 V. However, the sluggish reaction kinetics of O₂ evolution require an overpotential exceeding 400 mV (η > 400 mV) for the oxygen evolution reaction (OER, Eq. (3)). This high overpotential necessary for initiating the OER opens up the possibility of producing H₂O₂ during the multi-electron transfer process via WOR (Eq. (2)).

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An electrochemical or photoelectrochemical system designed exclusively for H_2O_2 production can be based on either a two-electron process (Eq. (4)) or a four-electron process (Eq. (5)). The four-electron process requires double the amount of charge to generate the same quantity of H_2O_2 as the two-electron process.

Due to this, significant efforts continue to focus on improving the (photo)electrochemical production of H_2O_2 via the two-electron process. Recently, the photoelectrochemical production of H_2O_2 through WOR and ORR was investigated in a system combining BiVO_4 as the photoanode and a gas diffusion electrode as the cathode [8]. The present study adopts a similar approach but utilizes hematite as the photoanode.

Hematite is currently a widely studied n-type semiconductor due to its potential use as a photoanode in various photoelectrochemical applications [9–11]. The most common application of hematite-based photoanodes (see Fig. 1b) is light-assisted water electrolysis, also known as PEC water splitting. However, hematite has also been utilized in other emerging photooxidation processes that are gaining attention, namely: (i) the photoelectrochemical oxidation (degradation) of organic impurities in water (e.g., salicylic acid or acid orange 7) [12–15], and (ii) the photoelectrochemical oxidation of inorganic ions (e.g., bromide anions) in aqueous solutions [16,17].

Hematite photoanodes can be prepared using various deposition techniques, including magnetron sputtering [18], hydrothermal synthesis [19], electrochemical deposition [20], and spray pyrolysis (SP) [21]. Spray pyrolysis is particularly favored due to its versatility, allowing adjustments in deposition temperature, spray flow rate, and fineness of the spray by modifying the excess pressure. Additionally, SP enables the deposition of coatings on larger substrates, making it easier to scale up for potential practical applications.

One of the main advantages of hematite is its ability to absorb visible light in the solar spectrum ($E_g = 2.1 \text{ eV}$, $\lambda_{\text{onset}} = 590 \text{ nm}$) [22], compared

to well-known titanium dioxide ($E_g = 3.2 \text{ eV}$, $\lambda_{\text{onset}} = 388 \text{ nm}$) [23]. However, hematite suffers from several limitations, such as low majority carrier mobility [24] and instability in acidic environments ($\text{pH} \leq 2$) [25]. The issue of low carrier mobility is typically addressed by doping hematite with elements like Sn [22,26] or Ti [21,27].

Regarding hematite's stability at low pH, even in highly acidic conditions (e.g., $\text{pH} < 2$, $0.01 \text{ M H}_2\text{SO}_4$), its dissolution rate is relatively low (0.171 nm/day) [21]. This rate can be further reduced by applying protective overlayers such as TiO_2 [28,29] or SnO_2 [30,31]. This enhanced stability is a notable advantage over photoanodes such as BiVO_4 , which are generally limited to neutral pH environments (typically buffers) because of their poor chemical and photoelectrochemical stability [32].

A gas diffusion electrode (Fig. 1c) addresses the mass transport limitations typically encountered in classic H-type cells with conventional metal plates or granular electrodes. This is achieved through its high porosity, operating current densities, and partial hydrophobicity [33] (Fig. 1e and f). The three-phase interface comprising gas, solid, and liquid phases characteristic of GDEs enables the uniform distribution of reactants and intermediate products across the catalyst surface. This makes GDEs particularly advantageous for O_2 reduction originating from air at the liquid-gas phase boundary. Additionally, the three-phase nature of GDEs aids in the separation of liquid and gaseous products during the ORR.

The development of efficient catalysts for integration into GDEs is crucial for minimizing the overpotential of the ORR. Metal phthalocyanine (MPc) is a thermally and chemically stable molecule with a flat structure, as illustrated in Fig. 1d. It features a metal-N4 structure, where a single metal atom (e.g., Sn, Co, or Ni) is coordinated to four nitrogen atoms within the molecule. This makes MPc one of the monoatomic catalysts with metal atoms serving as active sites. Incorporating MPc into GDEs is expected to enhance activity through electron accumulation in the central metal cation and improve selectivity by altering the properties of the cation. These changes in reactivity and selectivity are primarily attributed to differences in binding energies between the

Fig. 1. Schematic illustrations of a) PEC cell with $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3/\text{FTO}/\text{glass}$ photoanode (counter electrode – photoanode) in 1 M KHCO_3 ($\text{pH} 7.7$) bubbled with CO_2 and GDE (working electrode – cathode) in phosphate buffer ($\text{pH} 6.4$). The GDE was connected to compressed air. The PEC cell was equipped with a fused silica window and irradiated with the solar simulator (irradiance $100 \text{ mW}/\text{cm}^2$). The photoanode and cathode compartments were divided by a proton exchange membrane. d) Chemical structure of a SnPc, e) a three-layer architecture of an SnPc-modified GDE comprising a hydrophilic carbon top layer loaded with SnPc catalyst and a hydrophobic carbon mid-layer moulded onto a Ni mesh substrate, and f) basic principle of reactions at the three-phase interface. Photographs of b) $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3/\text{FTO}/\text{glass}$ photoanode and c) GDE (with SnPc) on Ni mesh.

reaction site and the reactants or intermediate products [34,35]. The mechanism of O₂ reduction on a catalyst can follow two distinct pathways: (i) the associative mechanism, where the O=O bond remains intact after O₂ adsorption, and (ii) the dissociative mechanism, where the O=O bond is cleaved upon O₂ adsorption. In the associative mechanism, activity increases with the adsorption of O₂ molecules and OOH*. The adsorption energy of the subsequent O* step also significantly influences selectivity. Lower adsorption energy favors the two-electron reduction reaction, resulting in higher selectivity. One potential explanation for variations in adsorption energy is the influence of the d-electron count of the central metal. For O₂ reduction, an increased number of d-electrons leads to an antibonding state in the metal-oxygen bond. This destabilizes the O* intermediate, enhancing selectivity [34].

This work aimed to study a system capable of producing hydrogen peroxide via both the oxygen reduction reaction and the water oxidation reaction. To achieve this, a cathode in the form of a gas diffusion electrode and a photoanode made of hematite (α -Fe₂O₃/FTO/glass) were utilized. The study focused on maximizing Faradaic efficiencies by investigating the effects of modifying the GDE with tin(II) phthalocyanine (SnPc) and selecting an optimal electrolyte for the cathode compartment. Additionally, the advantages of the photoelectrochemical process over the electrochemical process were demonstrated by comparing platinum and hematite as (photo)anodes. The novelty of this work lies in the use of hematite as the material for preparing the photoanode for the H₂O₂ generation via WOR reaction. Hematite was selected not only because it remains unexplored in this context but also due to its superior chemical and photoelectrochemical stability compared to other materials studied (e.g., WO₃ or BiVO₄). These properties make hematite particularly well-suited for long-term photoelectrochemical experiments, establishing it as a promising candidate for hydrogen peroxide production.

2. Experimental

2.1. Chemicals, electrode preparation, H₂O₂ analysis

Chemicals, materials, deposition and characterisation of hematite films, GDE preparation and measurements of H₂O₂ concentration are described in detail in [Supplementary information \(SI\)](#) ([Chapters S1.1–S1.4](#)).

2.2. Photoelectrochemical characterization

The photoelectrochemical cell was equipped with a fused silica window. The counter and reference electrodes were placed in a separate compartment, isolated from the working electrode by a proton exchange membrane. Experiments were primarily conducted in a two-electrode setup (GDE vs. counter electrode). The Ag/AgCl reference electrode was employed only when measuring the distribution of the applied bias across the α -Fe₂O₃ and the GDE. The gas diffusion electrode served as the cathode and was immersed in 30 mL of either 0.5 M phosphate buffer (pH 6.4) or 0.5 M Na₂SO₄ (pH 7.2). The catholyte was bubbled with either air or argon. For argon experiments, pre-bubbling was performed for 30 min before the start of the experiment. The anodic compartment contained hematite as the photoanode and 40 mL of 1 M potassium hydrogen carbonate (KHCO₃). To maintain the pH of the KHCO₃ solution, the anolyte was bubbled with CO₂, with a pre-bubbling duration of 30 min. The pH of the solutions was measured using a pH meter (Horiba Co. Ltd., F-74S, Japan). Measurements were conducted using a Hokuto Denko Co. Ltd. HSV-110 (Japan) potentiostat. For measurements involving a reference electrode (3 M KCl, $E_{\text{Ag/AgCl}} = 0.210$ V vs. NHE), a multimeter (Kyoritsu Corp., Japan) was used. Voltammetry and amperometry experiments were performed under front-side irradiation. A solar simulator (Peccell Technologies Co. Ltd., PEC-L15, 150 W Xe arc lamp, Japan) with an AM1.5 G filter and irradiance

of 1 sun (100 mW/cm²) served as the light source.

2.3. PEC performance of α -Fe₂O₃ and GDE

The photoelectrochemical performance of hematite or the GDE in the studied system was assessed by calculating the Faradaic efficiency. The FE for ORR and WOR was determined as the ratio of the electric current required for the formation of a product to the total electric current passed through the PEC system during the experiment (Eq. (6))

$$FE(\%) = \frac{z_{e^-} \cdot F \cdot r(X)}{i} \cdot 100 \% \quad (6)$$

where z_{e^-} is the number of electrons required for the formation of the product X, F is the Faraday constant (96 485 C/mol), $r(X)$ is the formation rate of the product (X) in mol/s and i is the measured (photo) current.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Physical characterization of α -Fe₂O₃ thin films and GDE

Based on previous work [21], Ti-doped hematite films with an optimized thickness of approximately 200 nm on FTO/glass substrates were fabricated using spray pyrolysis and characterized by XRD and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) (see [S1.2](#) in [SI](#)). As shown in [Fig. S1](#) (in [SI](#)), the deposited films consisted of phase-pure hematite, with no evidence of other iron oxides (e.g., FeO (wüstite) or Fe₃O₄ (magnetite)) that could negatively impact photoelectrochemical performance. The observed SnO₂ (cassiterite) signal is attributed to the selected substrate (FTO/glass). The top-view SEM morphology of the hematite layers is displayed in [Fig. S2](#) (in [SI](#)). The images reveal well-connected hematite particles with sharp edges, indicating good crystallinity, as further confirmed by XRD analysis. The gas diffusion electrode on nickel mesh was prepared following the same method described in our previous work [8,36] (see [S1.3](#) in [SI](#)). A photograph of the GDE, demonstrating its good mechanical stability, is shown in [Fig. 1c](#). The GDE had a diameter of 20 mm.

3.2. Oxygen reduction reaction on GDE

To investigate the electrochemical properties of the O₂ reduction reaction at the interface of a gas diffusion electrode modified with tin(II) phthalocyanine catalyst, linear sweep voltammetry (i - E_{cell}) and amperometry (j - t) measurements were conducted in a two-electrode configuration. E_{cell} is a potential applied between GDE and hematite photoanode. [Fig. 2](#) presents the i - E_{cell} curves for the GDE without and with SnPc incorporated into its hydrophilic layer, using two inlet gases: air and argon. As expected, a significant shift in the current onset potential (approximately 400 mV) was observed when the inlet gas was changed from argon to air. This shift confirms that ORR occurs at less negative potentials compared to the hydrogen evolution reaction. The incorporation of SnPc resulted only in very small (almost negligible) positive shift in the ORR onset potential.

[Fig. S3](#) in [SI](#) shows the potentials of the α -Fe₂O₃ photoanode and the GDE with SnPc as a function of applied bias (E_{cell}) ranging from 0 to -1.8 V (GDE vs. α -Fe₂O₃). Up to an applied bias of -1 V, the potentials of both electrodes increase linearly. However, for higher bias values under light irradiation, the voltage distribution across the two electrodes becomes asymmetric. This asymmetry is attributed to a greater increase in the potential of the α -Fe₂O₃ photoanode compared to the GDE. The observed behaviour is due to the maximum anodic current at the n-type photoanode, which occurs once critical band bending is achieved, i.e., when all charge carriers are effectively separated.

Fig. 2. i - E_{cell} curves of GDE (no SnPc) vs. α - Fe_2O_3 as photoanode with air as inlet gas (blue curve, circles) and GDE (with SnPc) vs. α - Fe_2O_3 with argon (black curve, squares) or air (blue curve, triangles) as inlet gases. As a catholyte 0.5 M phosphate buffer (pH 6.4) and as an anolyte 1 M KHCO_3 (pH 7.7) were used. The irradiated area of the α - Fe_2O_3 photoanode was 1.5 cm^2 (irradiation 100 mW/cm^2 (1 sun)).

3.2.1. Influence of SnPc

To further investigate and confirm the positive effect of SnPc incorporation in the hydrophilic layer of the gas diffusion electrode on the selectivity for the ORR, amperometry was performed at a bias of -1 V (GDE vs. α - Fe_2O_3) (Fig. 3a). The H_2O_2 concentration (see S1.4 in SI) was measured after 1, 3, and 5 h of polarization (one experiment per time point), and based on these measurements, the Faradaic efficiency was calculated using Eq. (6). As shown in Fig. 3, the presence of SnPc in the GDE had a beneficial impact on H_2O_2 generation via ORR, resulting in higher concentrations of hydrogen peroxide over time. Fig. 3b illustrates that the H_2O_2 concentration increased almost linearly and was approximately twice as high compared to the GDE without SnPc modification. This improvement translated to Faradaic efficiencies of around 50 % for the GDE with SnPc modification, whereas the GDE without SnPc achieved only about 30 % of FE over the same time. These Faradaic efficiencies demonstrate that the incorporation of SnPc as a catalyst significantly enhanced the selectivity for the ORR.

3.2.2. Influence of catholyte

The positive effect of GDE modification with SnPc was evaluated in two different electrolytes in the cathodic compartment: 0.5 M phosphate buffer (pH 6.4) and 0.5 M Na_2SO_4 (pH 7.2). Hematite was used as the photoanode in a 1 M KHCO_3 anolyte. As shown in Fig. S4a (in SI), a steady photocurrent value of approximately -0.4 mA/cm^2 was measured over a 5-h time interval. After 5 h, the concentration of H_2O_2 was $713 \text{ }\mu\text{M}$ in the Na_2SO_4 catholyte, which was roughly half of the concentration observed for the cell with 0.5 M phosphate buffer as the catholyte. The beneficial effect of the phosphate buffer on GDE performance in the studied PEC system was further confirmed by the calculation of the Faradaic efficiency. The FE for the phosphate buffer was more than twice that of the Na_2SO_4 solution (52 % vs. 24 %) (see Fig. 3b and Fig. S4b in SI). This result aligns with the findings of Shiraishi et al. [37], who reported that at high concentrations of H_2O_2 synthesized in photoelectrochemical systems, disproportionation reactions and H_2O_2 decomposition occur. Phosphate ions (H_2PO_4^-) stabilize hydrogen peroxide by suppressing these decomposition reactions. Simply put, phosphate ions associate with H_2O_2 via hydrogen bonding to form stable complexes, preventing its decomposition into water and oxygen.

3.2.3. Hematite as a counter electrode (comparison with Pt)

The production of H_2O_2 via ORR on the GDE was compared using two counter electrodes (CEs): platinum (electrochemical process) and hematite (photoelectrochemical process). As shown in Fig. 4, when hematite was used as the CE, the onset potential for ORR was significantly shifted in a favorable direction by up to 400 mV compared to platinum. This more favorable onset position for ORR with hematite as the CE can be attributed to the positive effect of the semiconductor's photopotential, which strongly enhances the PEC process.

To investigate the influence of the counter electrode (CE) on H_2O_2 production, amperometry was performed for 5 h using Pt. As shown in Fig. S5 (in SI), the use of Pt resulted in a lower photocurrent (-0.2 mA/cm^2) compared to hematite (Fig. 3a). Notably, when hematite was used as the CE, the H_2O_2 concentration after 1 h was 5.6 times higher, and after 5 hours approximately 18.7 times higher than with Pt. Specifically, the concentration increased from $37 \text{ }\mu\text{M}$ to $206 \text{ }\mu\text{M}$ after 1 h and from $73 \text{ }\mu\text{M}$ to $1260 \text{ }\mu\text{M}$ after 5 h. A similar trend was observed for Faradaic efficiencies. Although the current for Pt remained steady, the evolution of H_2O_2 over time did not exhibit a linear increase (Fig. 5). This resulted in a significant difference in Faradaic efficiencies: 12.8 % vs. 49.5 % after 1 h, and 4.5 % vs. 52.4 % after 5 h. When Pt was used as the CE, the charge was utilized for the ORR reaction far less efficiently compared to the system with the GDE and α - Fe_2O_3 as the photoanode (see Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. a) j - t curves for GDE without SnPc (black curve) and GDE with SnPc (blue curve) with α - Fe_2O_3 as a counter electrode, b) measured concentrations of H_2O_2 in μM (red curves, without SnPc – squares, with SnPc – circles) and calculated Faradaic efficiencies in % after 1, 3 and 5 h (black curves, without SnPc – squares, with SnPc – circles). Air was used as an inlet gas for GDE. As a catholyte, 0.5 M phosphate buffer (pH 6.4) and as an anolyte 1 M KHCO_3 (pH 7.4) bubbled with CO_2 were used. Irradiation 100 mW/cm^2 (1 sun). Applied bias -1 V (GDE vs. α - Fe_2O_3).

Fig. 4. i - E_{cell} curves of GDE (with SnPc) vs. counter electrodes (CEs): (i) α - Fe_2O_3 (black squares) and (ii) Pt (blue circles). Air was used as inlet gas for GDE. As a catholyte 0.5 M phosphate buffer (pH 6.4) and as an anolyte 1 M KHCO_3 (pH 7.7) were used. The active area of the platinum anode was 1.5 cm^2 . The same hematite area was irradiated with AM1.5 ($100 \text{ mW}/\text{cm}^2$).

Fig. 5. The measured concentration of H_2O_2 (red) in μM and calculated Faradaic efficiencies (black) in % after 1, 3 and 5 h for GDE (with SnPc) vs. counter electrodes: (i) α - Fe_2O_3 (squares) and (ii) Pt (circles). Air was used as an inlet gas for GDE. As a catholyte, 0.5 M phosphate buffer (pH 6.4) and as an anolyte 1 M KHCO_3 (pH 7.7) bubbled with CO_2 were used. Applied bias -1 V (GDE vs. α - Fe_2O_3).

3.3. H_2O_2 generation by water oxidation

As mentioned, the evolution of H_2O_2 is thermodynamically less favorable compared to O_2 evolution, with a potential difference of $E_{\text{H}_2\text{O}_2/\text{H}_2\text{O}} - E_{\text{O}_2/\text{H}_2\text{O}} = 0.547 \text{ V}$. Consequently, the practical implementation of photoelectrochemical WOR for H_2O_2 production remains largely unexplored. The decrease in reaction selectivity for H_2O_2 synthesis via the WOR (Eq. (2)), due to competition with the OER (Eq. (3)), can be mitigated through the selection of an appropriate electrolyte solution. Fuku et al. [38] demonstrated that the selectivity of H_2O_2 synthesis during the OER on a tungsten trioxide/bismuth vanadate photoanode was significantly enhanced by using a bicarbonate-containing solution as the electrolyte. In this system, HCO_3^- adsorbs onto the anode surface and participates in the oxidation reaction, forming percarbonate species such as HCO_4^- and $\text{C}_2\text{O}_6^{2-}$. For instance, the formation of HCO_4^- proceeds according to Eq. (7) [39]. The subsequent hydrolysis of these percarbonate species results in the production of H_2O_2 and the regeneration of HCO_3^- (Eq. (8)).

Bubbling CO_2 gas into the electrolyte solution can enhance H_2O_2 production by increasing the concentration of HCO_3^- and lowering the pH, as described by the equilibrium equations (Eqs. (S1)–(S3) in SI). H_2O_2 concentration measurements were conducted in the anolyte solution (1 M KHCO_3), where the hematite photoanode was placed. These measurements were performed using the most efficient configuration, combining the hematite photoanode with the GDE modified with SnPc (based on FE results, see Fig. 3b). The 1 M KHCO_3 solution used in this study is slightly alkaline (pH 8.4). The decrease in pH caused by CO_2 bubbling (to pH 7.7) suppresses H_2O_2 decomposition. However, H_2O_2 was only detected after 5 hours, with a concentration of approximately $0.05 \text{ mg}/\text{l}$ ($15 \mu\text{M}$), corresponding to an almost negligible FE value of 0.4 %. Similarly low H_2O_2 concentrations have been reported by Chao et al. [8], with values of $14 \mu\text{M}$ and $5.5 \mu\text{M}$ observed for WO_3 and BiVO_4 photoanodes, respectively, in combination with a GDE.

3.4. Comparison of ORR and WOR for H_2O_2 production

As described above and summarized in Table S1 (in SI), the highest H_2O_2 concentrations were achieved using the configuration of a hematite photoanode and a GDE (modified with SnPc) as the cathode, with 0.5 M phosphate buffer (pH 6.4) as the catholyte and air as the inlet gas for the GDE. This setup resulted in a Faradaic efficiency of 52.4 % after 5 h, producing $1260 \mu\text{M}$ of H_2O_2 in the electrolyte solution on the GDE side. For this optimal configuration, the concentration of H_2O_2 on the α - Fe_2O_3 side (anolyte: 1 M KHCO_3 , pH 7.7, bubbled with CO_2 to maintain the pH) was much lower, with an FE of only 0.4 %, corresponding to approximately $15 \mu\text{M}$ of H_2O_2 after 5 hours. Similarly low FEs for H_2O_2 production (0.3 %) have been reported for BiVO_4 photoanodes [8]. This was attributed to the fact that photogenerated carriers predominantly follow the four-electron pathway (Eq. (5)) to evolve O_2 , rather than the two-electron pathway (Eq. (4)) for H_2O_2 formation, despite both reactions being thermodynamically feasible for hematite as a photoanode (see Fig. S6 in SI).

4. Conclusions

Linear sweep voltammetry and long-term (5 h) amperometry experiments were conducted to evaluate the influence of various factors on the Faradaic efficiency of H_2O_2 generation via both the oxygen reduction reaction and water oxidation reaction. The system combined a hematite photoanode with a gas diffusion electrode, either unmodified or modified with tin(II) phthalocyanine (SnPc) incorporated into the hydrophilic layer of the GDE. The presence of hematite in the system led to a significant shift in the onset potential for ORR in a favorable direction by approximately 400 mV and resulted in a higher FE compared to platinum (Pt). In contrast, the SnPc modification of the GDE caused only a minor shift in the ORR onset potential but significantly increased the selectivity for ORR (30 vs. 50 % of FE). The stabilizing effect of 0.5 M phosphate buffer on H_2O_2 in the electrolyte was confirmed. The most effective configuration consisted of the hematite photoanode and the SnPc-modified GDE as the cathode, with 0.5 M phosphate buffer as the catholyte and air as the inlet gas. Under these conditions, steady-state FE values for H_2O_2 formation on the GDE reached approximately 50 % between 1 and 5 h. In comparison, the FE for H_2O_2 formation on hematite was only 0.4 %, even with the use of 1 M KHCO_3 and CO_2 bubbling to maintain pH. This result indicates that the reaction kinetics for H_2O_2 generation via WOR is not favorable. Our work has highlighted the importance of selecting a suitable electrolyte for hydrogen peroxide production via both ORR and WOR. The superiority of the

photoelectrochemical process over the electrochemical process was demonstrated by hematite's ability to reduce the onset potential for ORR. However, hematite alone did not show good performance in H₂O₂ generation via WOR, emphasizing the need for further research to identify materials that are both effective and stable for long-term production of H₂O₂.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Josef Krýsa: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Teruhisa Ohno:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Takumu Nakata:** Methodology, Investigation. **Tomas Imrich:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Data curation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.cattod.2025.115206](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cattod.2025.115206).

Data availability

The data presented in this study are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13164575>. Dataset of “Photoelectrochemical generation of H₂O₂ using hematite (α-Fe₂O₃) and gas diffusion electrode (GDE)” (Original data) (Zenodo).

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